

EXPRESS PROCEDURE FOR EVALUATION OF DURABILITY OF COMPLEX SHAPE PULTRUDED COMPOSITE PROFILES

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ABSTRACT

Pultruded composite profiles of different shapes are increasingly applied in civil engineering for new building constructions and renovation of the existing ones. These materials poses a set of high specific mechanical characteristics, comparatively safe fracture modes, high corrosion resistance, easy handling, but sometimes are used not enough efficiently because of several issues. One of such issue is environmental effects on composite stability and durability. Pultruded profiles often have quite complex shapes of their cross-section that makes difficult analytical calculation of the environmental effects.

The aim of this research is development of an analytical express procedure for evaluation of durability of complex shape pultruded composite profiles and reinforcing rods subjected to aggressive environmental factors.

The procedure includes next stages: 1) Express estimation of comparative aggressiveness of environmental factors; 2) Estimation of aggressive factor effects on the service characteristics of composite material; 3) Prediction of the dangerous influence of the environmental factors on composite profile. Moisture, high temperature, and thermal cycling are considered as the examples of aggressive environmental factors. The third stage includes the following principal steps: 3a) virtually splitting of a complex shape on simple ones; 3b) evaluation of environmental effect; 3c) virtually merging the environmental effect from the simple forms back to the complex one.

The procedure is illustrated on the thermal and moisture effects on I- and box-shape pultruded beams. Analytical estimation is compared with FEM calculations and proved with the experimental data for moisture effect. The investigation makes a contribution to the branches of advanced materials science and environmental sciences, civil engineering.

1. INTRODUCTION

The modern technology of manufacturing products from polymer composite materials (PCM) by pultrusion makes it possible to produce beams of complex shape with a given anisotropy of physical and mechanical properties. Since the properties of PCM significantly depend on the temperature of a material, which varies with the environment, for predicting the serviceability of products, it is important to be able to estimate environmental effects like temperature and moisture. A change in the temperature of a PCM with time can cause great thermal stresses leading to breaks of continuity of the PCM and consequently to its destruction [1-4]. With a change in temperature on the surface of a product, its equalization over the cross section of the beam occurs owing to heat transfer, which is described by the heat conduction equation. The time of the transient process depends on the gradient of temperatures on the surface and inside the product, on its geometry and sizes, and the properties of PCM. Moisture absorption reduces mechanical properties (stiffness, strength). Moisture effect depends on structure, properties of matrix, fibers and some other parameters.

However, the composite profiles often have more complex shape, such as H-shaped, W-shaped, box-like, etc. There is no exact analytical solutions of thermoconductivity or moisture diffusion equations for such shapes. Numerical modeling should be used to estimate the moisture content or temperature distribution of these profiles. However, this way is time-consuming, it requires high skills professionals. Numerical methods do not provide the necessary flexibility in the calculation when some changes in the profile geometry, environmental conditions, composition of materials take place. It is quite necessary to develop an approximate method for estimating the moisture content of the composite profile of complex shape. Using this method, it is possible with relatively simple formulas to quickly evaluate the kinetics and duration of the sorption process or temperature propagation and then predict the change of operational characteristics of the profile. The development of such method is **the main task** of the work. To solve this task following strategy is proposed. The express procedure should be stated in general and explained on some example cases of pultruded profiles like I-beam and box shape beam. Temperature and moisture will be assumed as two environmental factors affected on durability of composite profiles and basics of both conductivities should be mentioned. FEM calculation is assumed as an instrument to simulate both moisture and temperature propagation processes in profiles by full and simplified schemes to estimate errors and validity of such simplification. Results of FEM modelling and simplified calculation should be compared with experiments as a last step of validation.

2. EXPRESS PROCEDURE FOR EVALUATION OF DURABILITY OF COMPLEX SHAPE PULTRUDED COMPOSITE PROFILES

The complicated cross section of a pultrusion beam, with a certain degree of accuracy, for most cases may **virtually** be divided into simple components — **rectangles**. Obviously, the solution to the problem of heat or moisture transfer can also be presented in the form of superposition of analytical solutions for the simple constituents.

Figure 1: Pultruded profiles A and their splitted schemes B: a) I-beam, b) C-shape, c) box-shape, d) L-shape. Axis Y and Z coincide with main axes of symmetry of composite.

Such a simplification is useful for engineers and designers, since it allows one to make quick estimates of changes in the PCM properties with varying temperature by using relatively simple analytical formulas and to avoid the necessity of a complex and labor-consuming FEM simulation. As an example of such simplification, we will consider the replacement of the cross section of an I-beam by three rectangles. Example of such split for I-beam and some other profiles is given in Fig. 1. To substantiate such a replacement, we will compare the results of simulation of heat transfer for the entire I-beam and its separate constituent rectangles with account of anisotropy of heat conduction of the material. Thus e.g. for moisture content w of a profile it could be simply supposed

$$w(t) = \frac{\sum_i w_i(t) S_i}{\sum_i S_i}, \quad (1)$$

where w_i is moisture content of a profile element, S_i is element area. To prove validity of this procedure this simple analytical calculation will be compared with numerical FEM modelling and experimental results for moisture sorption.

3. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

3.1. Thermal conductivity

Fourier differential equation of heat conduction for an anisotropic body in a Cartesian system of coordinates whose x , y , and z axes coincide with symmetry axes of the material looks [5, 6]

$$c\rho \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \lambda_x \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + \lambda_y \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + \lambda_z \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2}, \quad (2)$$

where λ is the heat conductivity coefficient describing the rate of heat transfer, c and ρ are the thermal capacity and density of the material, respectively. Equation (2) was derived for constant characteristics c , ρ , λ_x , λ_y , and λ_z of the material.

This equation, along with initial and boundary conditions, composes the problem of heat conduction, whose solution is found analytically or numerically, depending on the type of boundary conditions, geometry of the product, and anisotropy of properties of the material [7-9]. As a result of solution of this equation, the distribution of temperatures in the body at an arbitrary instant of time and the integral characteristic of the process of heat transfer, namely the change in the average temperature $\overline{\Delta T}$ of the body in time, are found.

Analytical solutions to heat conduction problems for anisotropic bodies with boundary conditions of the first kind, i.e., the stationary problems of heat conduction, were obtained for simplest geometrical forms, in particular, to the one-dimensional problem for a plane plate [7-9]. The solution of the three-dimensional problem for a rectangular parallelepiped is constructed as the superposition of three independent solutions of one-dimensional problems. For bodies of a complex shape, with account of anisotropy of the properties of PCM, the problems of heat transfer are solved by numerical methods, in particular, by the finite-element method (FEM), with the use of computer programs, for example, ANSYS [10, 11].

The problem of heat conduction was solved in a two-dimensional statement. Such a solution is allowable for sufficiently long beams. If the ratio between the length and the greatest size in the cross section exceeds 10 (typically hundreds!), the influence of end faces of the beam can be neglected. The beam was uniformly loaded with a thermal load along its length. The error arising upon a rough calculation of the kinetics of heat transfer was estimated during a numerical modeling process for an I-

beam according to three calculation schemes (Fig. 1): for the entire cross section (scheme A), for the section divided into rectangles (schemes B).

The use of the simplified calculation scheme B instead of the scheme A brings an error in calculation of the kinetics of heat transfer because the heat transfer between the flanges and the web is not taken into account. This error shows up in different rates of change in the average temperatures of the entire cross section and its elements. For a quantitative estimation of the error, we found the relative difference between the average temperatures of the cross section and its elements determined by registering it at the same instant of time for the scheme B and by comparing their values with those for the scheme A:

$$\delta = \frac{\bar{T}_B}{\bar{T}_A} - 1, \quad (3)$$

where $\bar{T}_{B,A}$ is the average temperature in the cross section (or in its element). Such estimation of the error allowed us to avoid the consideration of the distribution of temperatures all over the cross section of the beam.

3.2. Fick's model for moisture sorption by orthotropic composite

The concentration of moisture and its integral content $w(t)$ in the composite profile versus time t and the coordinates x, y, z in many cases are well described by the Fick's second law. Moisture content in 3D case for parallelepiped is calculated as a superposition 1D solutions [12].

$$w_3(t) = w_{3\infty} - \frac{8w_{3\infty}}{\pi^6} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{[1 - (-1)^k]^2 [1 - (-1)^n]^2 [1 - (-1)^m]^2}{k^2 n^2 m^2} \exp[-\lambda_{k,n,m}^2 t], \quad (4)$$

$$\text{where } \lambda_{k,n,m}^2 = \lambda_k^2 + \lambda_n^2 + \lambda_m^2 = \left(\frac{\pi k}{l}\right)^2 D_x + \left(\frac{\pi n}{b}\right)^2 D_y + \left(\frac{\pi m}{h}\right)^2 D_z.$$

Expression (4) is also the basis of the experimental determination of diffusion coefficients D_x, D_y, D_z orthotropic according to the results of tests of flat samples.

4. CALCULATION METHOD

Numerical simulation of temperature transfer in composite profile was performed in ANSYS. From the results of numerical simulation of the transfer process, the average temperatures in the entire cross section and in its elements, namely flanges and web, were determined. The initial results of the finite-element solution are the values of nodal temperatures at an instant of time j . Thus, for an i th node, we have T_{ij} . The average temperature of a k th FE, determined by n nodes, at the instant of time j is

$$T_{(k)}^j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n T_{i(k)}^j}{n}.$$

The average temperature in the cross section including m FEs is

$$T^j = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^m T_{(k)}^j S_k}{\sum_{k=1}^m S_k},$$

where S_k is the area of a k th FE in the range considered. The average temperature was found during a successive calculation, employing the temperature determined at the previous step (the initial temperature was assigned in determining the initial conditions):

$$T^j = T^{j-1} + \Delta T^{j-1 \rightarrow j}.$$

The accuracy of calculation of average temperatures in the cross section with the use of the secondary result of the finite-element solution depends on two factors: the density of the finite-element mesh on external surfaces of the model (i.e., the distances between the nodes on the external surface of model) and the value of the calculation step in time.

The algorithms of determination of average temperatures in the cross section were realized by means of the ANSYS Parametric Design Language.

5. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Changes in moisture content of the pultruded FRP profiles and samples cut from the profiles were determined as change their weight after soaking in water at room temperature of about 20 °C. To accelerate the moisture sorption process, some samples of PCM in water maintained at elevated temperatures of 50 and 70 °C.

	GFRP with polyester matrix		CFRP with epoxy matrix		
$T, \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	20	70	20	50	70
$D_x \times 10^5, \text{ mm}^2/\text{h}$	851	151	27	200	900
$D_y \times 10^5, \text{ mm}^2/\text{h}$	453	66	14	90	400
$D_z \times 10^5, \text{ mm}^2/\text{h}$	148	53	10.5	50	280
$w_\infty, \%$	1.35	1.35	0.65	0.65	0.65

Table 1: The diffusivity and equilibrium moisture content of PKM at different temperatures.

Anisotropy indexes of in the plane of section D_y/D_z GFRP and CFRP composites at 20 °C (3.1 and 1.3, respectively), are quite similar at 70 °C (1.3 and 1.4).

6. CALCULATION RESULTS

6.1. GFRP I-beam.

Numerical solution of a problem of moisture diffusion in I-beam was performed for full and simplified calculation schemes.

Results of moisture sorption experiment and analytical calculation using simplified scheme are given in Fig. 2. Deviation was calculated by expression similar to (3). As it is seen from the figure, moisture sorption process is close to saturation after three years. The deviation of calculation is approx. 10% after 100 h of sorption and close to zero after 200 days.

Quite small values of deviation proofs that simplified calculation is acceptable for engineering applications.

Figure 2: Moisture sorption by pultruded profile, experiment (dots) and calculation (solid line).
Deviation of analytical calculation to experiment.

6.2. CFRP box-beam.

One more profile tested was box shape carbon fibre reinforced beam Fig. 1c. Numerical modelling was also performed for full and simplified calculation schemes Fig. 1A and B. Calculated value of moisture content of the profile specimens was compared with experimental in Fig. 3. It is seen that maximal deviation of experimental and calculated values is observed for initial stage of sorption process. This deviation may be caused by different reasons as inaccuracy of experimental results, diffusion parameters evaluation, nonfickian sorption behaviour of the composite, etc. Meanwhile calculated sorption curve is in good agreement with experimental results, accuracy is acceptable for engineering applications.

Figure 3: Time dependence of average moisture content of box shape profile; calculation (line) and experiment (dots).

7. SIMPLIFIED ANALYTICAL CALCULATION

Simplified analytical calculation of moisture content changes with time for I-beam illustrates application of the method. I-beam was virtually splitted on three components: two flanges and web (Fig. 1a). Simplified analytical calculation for web was made by formula

$$w_w = w_w^\infty - 8 \frac{w_r^\infty - w_r^0}{\pi^2} \sum_{k=1}^N \left[\frac{1}{(2k-1)^2} e^{-\left[\left(\frac{\pi(2k-1)}{R_y} \right)^2 D_y \right] t} \right] \quad (5)$$

and for each flange by

$$w_f = w_f^\infty - 64 \frac{w_f^\infty - w_f^0}{\pi^4} \sum_{m=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^N \left[\frac{1}{(2m-1)^2} \cdot \frac{1}{(2k-1)^2} e^{-\left[\left(\frac{\pi(2m-1)}{R_y} \right)^2 D_y + \left(\frac{\pi(2k-1)}{R_x} \right)^2 D_x \right] t} \right]. \quad (6)$$

Total moisture content of the profile according to (1) was estimated as

$$w = \frac{w_w S_w + 2w_f S_f}{S_w + 2S_f} \quad (7)$$

were S_w and S_f are section areas of web and flange respectively. Comparison of calculation errors (3) for web (5), flange (6), and full profile (7) are given in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Calculation errors of average moisture content for web (5) (line 2), flange (6) (line 1), and full profile (7) (line 3).

It is seen from Fig. 4 that maximal error for profile elements is within 1-3% and for full profile is less than 1%. This accuracy is well enough for engineering applications.

CONCLUSIONS

Express procedure for estimation of durability of complex shape pultruded composite profiles is suggested. The procedure was implemented on moisture sorption of I- and box-shape pultruded profiles and thermal conductivity of I-shape profile. The procedure suppose that complicated cross section of a pultrusion beam for most cases may **virtually** be divided into simple components — **rectangles**. The solution to the problem of heat or moisture transfer can also be presented in the form of superposition of analytical solutions for the simple constituents.

The calculation error of the average temperature in the elements of cross section depends on the time of the transient process: it is maximum at the initial stage (6-9% for the flange and below 3.5% for the web), and decreases to 0.7% by the end of the process. The peak of error in determining the average temperature of the flange occurs directly at the initial stage of the process; for the web, it falls on the time equal to 0.07-0.13 of the total duration of the process.

Thus, the simplification of the calculation scheme does not bring a significant error in estimating the kinetics of heat or moisture transfer for a beam of a complex cross section. The arising errors are allowable for engineering calculation. The calculation scheme suggested can be recommended as a basis for creating a quick technique for calculating the heat transfer in beams of a complex shape. Such a simplification is useful for engineers and designers, since it allows one to make quick estimates of changes in the PCM properties with varying temperature by using relatively simple analytical formulas and to avoid the necessity of a complex and labor-consuming FEM simulation.

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